
NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF NAPOLEON'S THEOREM IN 3D

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we investigate the precision of measuring the internal angles of a presumed regular tetrahedron. Through rigorous numerical analysis, we demonstrate that the observed variation of the percentage error, limited to a maximum of 1.42%, and the Coefficient of Variation (CV), capped at $CV = 0.03$, can be attributed to the finite methods employed in our computations. These findings are consistent with the analytical results derived from the extension of Napoleon's theorem to arbitrary dimensions. Our results not only reaffirm the validity of Napoleon's theorem in three dimensions but also shed light on the inherent limitations and accuracy of computational methods in geometric analysis.

Keywords Napoleon's theorem · Numerical error · Simplices

1 Introduction

In the exploration of three-dimensional geometry, we embark on a numerical journey to investigate the extensions of classical theorems. Our focus lies on Napoleon's Theorem, a captivating result that unveils the symmetry within equilateral triangles. However, as we venture into the three-dimensional realm of regular tetrahedra, we acknowledge the imperfections that arise in our numerical analyses.

It is known that Napoleon Bonaparte (Napoleon I) devoted some time to mathematics, especially he was interested in geometry. There are some theorems, points, facts named after him or attributed to him; for example, Napoleon's theorem, Napoleon's points, Napoleon's famous problem and others [1].

1.1 Background

Napoleon's Theorem, a jewel of Euclidean geometry, asserts the formation of an equilateral triangle from the centers of equilateral triangles constructed on the sides of a given triangle. Intrigued by the prospect of extending this theorem to three dimensions, we delve into the realm of regular tetrahedra.

The classic Napoleon's theorem states that (see Fig. 1 to address the notation used in this work):

If equilateral triangles $\triangle A'CA$, $\triangle CC'B$ and $\triangle BB'A$ are erected externally on the sides of any triangle $\triangle ABC$, then their centers M , N , and O , respectively, form an equilateral triangle (the outer Napoleon triangle) [2].

Figure 1: Napoleon's theorem in 2 Dimensions. The GeoGebra® construction can be downloaded from <https://zenodo.org/records/10578114>

Napoleon's theorem has already been generalized using the idea of simplices [3, 4, 5, 6]. The procedure of extending Napoleon's theorem to any dimension could be outlined as follows:

- **Understanding Simplices:** In geometry, a simplex is a generalization of the notion of a triangle to higher dimensions. A 0-simplex is a point, a 1-simplex is a line segment, a 2-simplex is a triangle, a 3-simplex is a tetrahedron, and so on [3, 4, 5].
- **Higher-Dimensional Triangulations:** Consider the higher-dimensional analogs of triangles, such as tetrahedra (3D), pentachora (4D), and so on. These are simplices in higher dimensions [3, 4, 5].
- **Extension of Constructions:** Extend the idea of constructing equilateral figures on the faces of a simplex. For example, instead of constructing equilateral triangles on the edges of a tetrahedron, consider constructing equilateral tetrahedra on its faces [3, 4, 5].
- **Centers of Equilateral Figures:** Investigate the centers or centroids of these higher-dimensional equilateral figures. Determine whether there are interesting relationships among these centers [7, 8].
- **Use of Linear Algebra:** The generalization process often involves the use of linear algebra and vector spaces to handle the higher-dimensional geometric relationships [3, 5].

Extending Napoleon's theorem into three or more dimensions holds several significant implications and applications:

1. **Geometric Analysis:** By extending Napoleon's theorem into higher dimensions, mathematicians gain deeper insights into the geometric properties of polytopes beyond three dimensions. This expands the toolkit for geometric analysis and exploration. [9, 10]
2. **Computational Geometry:** The extension allows for the development of computational algorithms and tools for analyzing the spatial relationships and symmetries of higher-dimensional figures. This is valuable in fields such as computer graphics, robotics, and computer-aided design (CAD).[11, 12]
3. **Topology:** The study of higher-dimensional spaces and their properties is fundamental in topology. Extending Napoleon's theorem provides new examples and insights into the topology of higher-dimensional polytopes and their symmetries.[13, 14]
4. **Mathematical Visualization:** Visualization techniques for higher-dimensional objects are challenging but essential for understanding their properties. Extending Napoleon's theorem provides opportunities for developing new visualization methods and tools for representing higher-dimensional geometry.[15, 16]
5. **Applications in Physics and Engineering:** Higher-dimensional geometry has applications in theoretical physics, engineering, and other scientific disciplines. Understanding the symmetries and structures of higher-dimensional objects can lead to insights into complex physical systems and the design of novel materials and structures.[17, 18]

- 6. Mathematical Education:** Exploring Napoleon's theorem in higher dimensions can serve as an engaging and challenging topic for students learning about geometry and spatial reasoning. It encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills while introducing them to advanced mathematical concepts.[19, 20]

Overall, extending Napoleon's theorem into three or more dimensions opens up new avenues for exploration and discovery in mathematics and its applications across various disciplines.

1.2 Numerical Congruence and Understanding Numerical Imperfections

Our approach involves a statistical examination of the angles and sides within the regular tetrahedron. Instead of rigidly adhering to exact 60-degree angles, our exploration allows for statistical variations, reflecting the inherent limitations of numerical methods, such as those employed in tools like GeoGebra®.

We intend to showcase that the internal angles may deviate slightly from the ideal 60 degrees, leading to small numerical errors. However, these discrepancies, expressed through averages, standard deviations, and other statistical measures, do not undermine the essence of Napoleon's Theorem in three dimensions. Instead, they underscore the finite nature of our computational tools.

The imperfections observed are not a disproof but rather an inherent characteristic of employing numerical methods in a finite computational environment. Our aim is to foster an appreciation for the resilience of mathematical theorems in the face of computational limitations, highlighting the robust nature of mathematical truths beyond the constraints of numerical precision.

1.3 Contributions and Expectations

Our contributions extend beyond numerical analyses. By showcasing the statistical congruence within regular tetrahedra, we hope to inspire discussions on the interplay between classical theorems and computational methodologies. As we navigate the nuanced landscape of three-dimensional geometry, we anticipate a renewed appreciation for the enduring validity of Napoleon's Theorem and its potential extensions into higher dimensions.

In the subsequent sections, we delve into the intricacies of our numerical exploration, providing insights into the statistical nuances and their implications for the broader understanding of geometric truths in three-dimensional space.

2 Napoleon's Theorem in 3D using Tetrahedra

Extension of Napoleon's Theorem into 3D, can be done using a tetrahedron, which need not be regular, and over every one of the faces of this *base* tetrahedron, regular tetrahedra are to be constructed.

Without loss of generality, and because Napoleon's theorem in 2D essentially says that the base triangle can be deformed in any way, one of the faces of the base tetrahedron can be changed in shape according to the base triangle of its 2-dimensional counterpart, as can be seen in Fig.(2) and Fig.(3).

The expected result, is a regular tetrahedron constructed from the centroids of all the tetrahedra that in turned were built upon all the faces of the base tetrahedron. As a reminder, in a regular tetrahedron, all faces are equilateral triangles, and all internal angles are congruent. Since an equilateral triangle has each angle measuring 60 degrees, the internal angles of a regular tetrahedron also measure 60 degrees each. Therefore, all four internal angles of a regular tetrahedron are equal and measure 60 degrees. This last statement is what is going to be analyzed with statistical tools in the following section.

3 Reconciling Imperfection and Theorem Validity

3.1 Using a slider, and angles for resulting tetrahedron

As it was explained in section 1.1, and show in Fig.1, the base triangle (the green one) is formed with the points $\{A, B, C\}$. For the y coordinate a slider was set up, such that

$$C = (1.5, a), 1 \leq a \leq 2.6 \tag{1}$$

The increments are $\Delta a = 0.05$, resulting in 32 measurements. This number of measurements is considered sufficient, as the consistent smallness of the numerical errors incurred has been observed. This is in line with Ronald A. Fisher's work on the probable error of a coefficient of correlation from a small sample [21].

Figure 2: Napoleon's theorem in 3 Dimensions. The GeoGebra® construction can be downloaded from <https://zenodo.org/records/10578114>

Figure 3: Napoleon's theorem in 3 Dimensions (another perspective). The GeoGebra® construction can be downloaded from <https://zenodo.org/records/10578114>

This accomplish the purpose of transforming the base triangle, and thus the centroids of the equilateral triangles built upon that changing triangle will be modified, but there will always be an equilateral triangle constructed from those "floating" centroids (purple triangle, that looks upside down, with respect to the green triangle). The green triangle in 2D serves in turn as one of the faces of the base tetrahedron, which when transformed will also transform all the tetrahedrons built upon the base tetrahedron, their centroids will change and the tetrahedron built from those centroids (the conclusion of the theorem in 3D) will form a regular tetrahedron (see Figs.23, and the animation in the file <https://zenodo.org/records/10578114>).

Here we collect the measures of the four internal angles of the resulting tetrahedron, to be verified if it fulfills the criteria for being regular. Let the set of internal angles of the resulting tetrahedron be $\zeta = \{\lambda, \theta, \iota, \kappa\}$, so for example $\zeta = \{63.22, 59.48, 60.22, 60.26\}$, when $a = 1$, and $\zeta = \{59.14, 59.99, 60.41, 60\}$, when $a = 2.6$. Clearly,

$$\lambda \neq \theta \neq \iota \neq \kappa \neq 60^\circ \quad (2)$$

And only sometimes, some angles actually measure 60° . However, this does not necessarily disproves the fact that Napoleon's theorem is valid in three or more dimensions, as it will be shown by the following statistical analysis.

3.2 Statistics of angles and error in congruences

Let the average of the set of angles $\mu = \bar{\zeta}$, the standard deviation $\sigma(\zeta) = \sigma$ [22]. Define the *percent error* δ as [22]

$$\delta = 100\% \times \frac{|60^\circ - \mu|}{60^\circ} \quad (3)$$

Also, define the Coefficient of variation CV as [22]

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \quad (4)$$

Using 3 the percentage error varies from 0.01% to 1.42%. Using 4, the CV changes varies from 0.01 to 0.03. Now, suppose that we express the numerical error as

$$|\delta| \leq \varepsilon = 1.42\% \quad (5)$$

This is equivalent to $0.852^\circ \approx 51' < 1^\circ$. This should be enough to realize that the numerical error while constructing Napoleon's theorem is fairly consistent with its analytic counterpart, thus encouraging to follow on similar steps for other types of computational animations that may illustrate Napoleon's theorem in any dimension.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, our study has revealed that the observed variation in the percentage error (maximum 1.42%) and the Coefficient of Variation (maximum $CV = 0.03$) of the internal angles of a presumed regular tetrahedron, resulting from the adjustment of one of the base tetrahedron's points, remains within acceptable limits. These variations, albeit small, can be attributed to the inherent limitations of the finite methods employed in our analysis. Importantly, our findings are fully consistent with the analytical results derived from the extension of Napoleon's theorem to arbitrary dimensions. Thus, our study not only reaffirms the validity of Napoleon's theorem in three dimensions but also underscores the need for careful consideration of computational methods in geometric analysis.

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